

Terpenoids. Part XXXII : Synthesis of β -Cubebene

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1-Diazo-4(3-isopropyl-6-methyl-1-cyclohexene)2-butanone prepared from 3(3-isopropyl-6-methyl-1-cyclohexene) propanoyl chloride, on decomposition with anhydrous copper sulphate in refluxing *n*-hexane yields 5, 6 cyclohexano-7-isopropyl-10-methyl-bicyclo (3,1,0) hexan-2-one which when submitted to Wittig's reaction with methylene-triphenyl-phosphorane furnishes β -Cubebene.

β -Cubebene, the tricyclic sesquiterpene, isolated from commercial cubeb oil, has been assigned the constitution (I) on the basis of physical and chemical evidences¹.

β -Cubebene on ozonolysis yields a ketone whose formulation represented as (II) has been supported through I.R., U.V. and N.M.R. studies by the Japanese workers¹. In the present investigations, we focussed our attention to the synthesis of the compound (II), as this ketone appeared to be the most suitable candidate for conversion to β -cubebene(I), by the application of Wittig's reaction² with methylene-triphenyl-phosphorane which results in the fixation of exocyclic double bond beyond any doubt.

The present synthetic approach is based upon the recent observations³ that α -diazo-ketone possessing an olefinic bond at a suitable distance, decomposes involving intramolecular reaction in the presence of catalytic amount of anhydrous copper sulphate, affording thereby a cyclic ketone having conjugation with cyclopropane ring³⁻⁴.

1. Y. Ohta, T. Sakai and Y. Hirose, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1966, 6365.
2. Greenwald, Chaykovsky and Corey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.
3. M. M. Fawzi and C. D. Gutchi, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 1390.
4. F. Medina and F. Manjarrey, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 1807.

The chart given below illustrates the sequence of the reactions employed :

2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexanone (III) on reaction with ethyl formate in anhydrous benzene in the presence of sodium methoxide, at low temperature produced 2-formyl-3-methyl-6-isopropylcyclohexanone (IV) in excellent yields. It gave coloration with alcoholic ferric-chloride solution. The compound (IV), when subjected to lithium aluminium hydride reduction⁵ afforded a mixture of carbinols (V) and (VI) in which (V) predominates⁵. However, no attempt was made to separate the two allylic alcohols as both these carbinols on treatment with phosphorus tribromide in ether afforded the same allylic bromide (VII)⁶.

5. S. Searls Jr. and M. E. Harley, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 1969.

6. J. D. White and D. N. Gupta, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 5364.

The bromide (VII) when reacted upon with diethylmalonate in presence of tertiary butoxide in tertiary butyl alcohol gave the diester (VIII) in 60% yield. The compound (VIII) was hydrolysed with alkali under usual conditions to form the diacid (IX) as a viscous liquid which on decarboxylation at 160–180° (oil bath) in the presence of glass-powder⁷ produced 3(3-isopropyl-6-methyl-1-cyclohexene) propanoic acid (X). The acid (X) on refluxing with thionyl chloride in anhydrous benzene gave the corresponding acid chloride (XI) in quantitative yields. The acid chloride (XI) on treatment with ethereal solution of diazomethane under usual conditions^{3,4} generated α -diazoketone (XII). The α -diazoketone (XII) thus obtained was decomposed with catalytic amount of anhydrous copper sulphate in refluxing *n*-hexane^{3,4} to give the desired tricyclic-ketone II. The identity of the compound was established by comparison of its I.R. spectrum with that of the ketone obtained from the naturally occurring hydrocarbon (I)*.

The ketone (II) when subjected to the Wittig's reaction with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide in presence of methyl sulphanyl carbanion in dimethylsulphoxide according to the method described by Corey and Coworkers² yielded the title compound. The synthetic hydrocarbon was chromatographed over neutral alumina for purification. The identity of this compound was confirmed by comparison of its I.R. and N.M.R. spectra with that of the naturally occurring hydrocarbon.*

EXPERIMENTAL

Boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses are by B. M. Anand and L. K. Khullar, microanalysts of our department. I.R. spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer infraord with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid film.

2-formyl-3-methyl-6-isopropyl cyclohexanone (IV) : Ethyl formate (56.0 g) was added to a stirred and cooled suspension of 40.5 g. of sodium methoxide in 400 ml. of benzene. To this mixture was introduced slowly 2-isopropyl-5-methyl cyclohexanone (III) (77.0 g.) with continuous stirring during an hour. The contents were stirred overnight at room temperature and poured into crushed ice. The aqueous layer was separated and benzene portion was thoroughly washed with dilute sodium hydroxide (5%, 100 ml.). The alkali extract was mixed with aqueous phase and the combined aqueous phase was once washed with benzene and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting oil was taken up in ether. The ether-extract was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). After the removal of the solvent, the residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure to give the formyl derivative (IV), yield (72.8 g.; 80%), b.p. 135–40/5 mm. $^{20}\eta_D$ 1.4822. (Found : C, 72.15; H, 9.99; Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$: C, 72.53; H, 9.89).

Reduction of 2-formyl-3-methyl-6-isopropyl cyclohexanone : To a well stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (7.0 g.) in anhydrous ether (350 ml), was introduced 2-formyl-3-methyl-6-isopropyl cyclohexanone (IV) (45.5 g.) in 250 ml. of ether, at such a rate so as to maintain ether at a gentle reflux. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux overnight with continuous stirring. It was cooled and hydrolysed with 20% sodium carbonate solution

7. D. K. Bannerjee, and P. S. Halwe, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 869.

(250 ml). The ether solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and removal of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation gave the mixture of 2-methylene-3-methyl-6-isopropyl cyclohexan-1-ol (V) and the carbinol (VI) b.p. 90–108/8 mm. (Found : C, 78.20; H, 12.22; Calc. for $C_{10}H_{20}O$: C, 78.51; H, 11.98).

2-Bromomethyl-3-methyl-6-isopropyl-1-cyclohexene (VII) : The mixture of the above carbinols (24.0 g.) in 350 ml of anhydrous ether was treated dropwise with phosphorus tribromide (13.0 g.) during half an hour in the dark. The solution was refluxed for 3 hrs, cooled and poured in iced water, shaking and extracted three times with ether. The ether extracts were washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water (twice) and dried (Na_2SO_4). After the evaporation of the solvent, there was obtained the bromide (VII) (29.7 g., 90% yield) which was not distilled and used for the further reaction.

Ethyl 2-ethoxycarbonyl-3(3-isopropyl-6-methyl-1-cyclohexene) Propanoate (VIII) : To a cooled solution of potassium tertiary butoxide (prepared from potassium metal 3.90 g. and tertiary butanol 150 ml) was added diethylmalonate (16.0 g.) To the resulting potassium derivative, was introduced dropwise the above bromide (VII) (23.1 g.) and the mixture was refluxed for 10 hr. on a steam bath. Excess of tertiary butanol was removed under diminished pressure. Water was added to the residue, the organic layer was taken up in ether and dried (Na_2SO_4). After the removal of the solvent, the fraction distilling at 160–165/10 mm. was collected (18.68 g., 60% yield). I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1740 cm^{-1} (—ester). (Found : C, 70.05; H, 9.47; Calc. for $C_{18}H_{30}O_4$: C, 69.64; H, 9.74).

3(3-isopropyl-6-methyl-1-cyclohexene) propanoic acid (X) : The above diester (15.5 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of potassium hydroxide (6.0 g.), water (10 ml) and methanol (100 ml) for 10 hr. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue after cooling was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The organic material was extracted with ether and dried (Na_2SO_4). After the removal of the solvent, there was obtained the diacid (IX) as a viscous material (10.2 g., 80.3% yield).

The above diacid was not distilled, mixed with glass powder (0.5 g.) and treated to $160\text{--}180^\circ$ (oil bath) for 3 hr. The contents were cooled and taken up in ether. The solvent was stripped off and the residue on fractionation under reduced pressure gave the acid (X), b.p. 145–150/6 mm (5.5 g.), 60% yield, $^{20}\eta_D$ 1.4770, I.R. spectrum peaks : 3150–2850 (S-broad) (C-H and associated-OH), 1710 cm^{-1} (Carbonyl), (Found : C, 72.26; H, 9.78; Calc. for $C_{13}H_{22}O_2$: C, 75.63; H, 11.97).

3(3-isopropyl-6-methyl-1-cyclohexene) propanoyl chloride (XI) : A solution of the above acid (X) (5.25 g.), benzene (50 ml.) and thionyl chloride (3.0 g.) was heated under reflux till the evolution of HCl gas had ceased. Excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue on fractionation furnished the acid chloride (XI), b.p. 125/4 mm (5.0 g, 88% yield). $^{20}\eta_D$ 1.4650. (Found : C, 68.80; H, 9.50; Cl, 16.15; Calc. for $C_{13}H_{21}OCl$: C, 68.70; H, 9.19; Cl, 15.54).

5,6-cyclohexano-7-isopropyl-10-methyl-bicyclo (3.1,0) hexan-2-one (II) : 4.0 g. of the above acid chloride in ether was slowly added to an ice cold solution of 0.1 mole of diazomethane in 250 ml. of dry ether. The contents were allowed to stand at room temperature

for 3 hr. After the evaporation of the solvent, the resulting α -diazoketone (XII) obtained as a yellow oil was used without further purification (I.R. spectrum : 2100, 1645 cm^{-1} characteristic of α -diazoketone³). The diazoketone was dissolved in 300 ml. of *n*-hexane, treated with 1.0 g. of anhydrous copper sulphate and refluxed for 18 hr. The solvent was then largely removed, the infra-red spectrum of the residue was checked for disappearance of the bands characteristic of the diazoketone. The ketone (II) thus generated was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 145–50/4 mm. The infra-red spectrum of the ketone was found to be identical with infra-red spectrum of the ketone obtained from β -cubebene¹. I.R. spectrum : Characteristic peaks at 1715 ($> \text{C} = \text{O}$), 1025 (cyclopropane) and other peaks at 2950, 2850, 1490, 1470, 1460, 1450, 1280, 1250, 1180, 1150, 1115, 920, 910, 870 and 820 cm^{-1} . Lit. reports peaks at 2950, 2850, 1715, 1485, 1470, 1460, 1450, 1280, 1250, 1178, 1150, 1115, 1025, 920, 910, 870 and 820 cm^{-1} *. (Found : C, 81.87; H, 10.9; Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$: C, 81.50; H, 10.75).

β -Cubebene (I) : A solution of methyl sulphinyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen from sodium hydride (1.1 g.) 50% and freshly distilled dimethyl sulphoxide (7.5 ml). The solution was cooled in a cold water bath and stirred during addition on methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide (5.8 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (15 ml) whereupon the reddish colour of methylene triphenyl phosphorane was produced. After stirring at the room temperature for 15 min., the ketone (II) (1.6 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (10 ml) was added and stirring continued for 5 hrs at 60°. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into cold water. The organic material was taken up in light petroleum and washed thrice with water. After the removal of the solvent, the residue was filtered through a neutral alumina column, (elution with petroleum ether 40–60). The synthetic hydrocarbon was characterised through its I.R. and N.M.R. spectra. I.R. spectrum : Characteristic peaks at 3080, 1615 and 860 cm^{-1} ($> \text{C} = \text{H}_2$), 1030 (cyclopropane) and other peaks at 1490, 1470, 1455, 1300, 1260, 1200, 1170, 1130, 1060, 960, 940, 875, 840 and 810 cm^{-1} . Lit. reports peaks at 3080, 1615, 860, 1030, 1485, 1470, 1450, 1300, 1260, 1200, 1170, 1130, 1060, 960, 940, 875, 840 and 810 cm^{-1} *.

N.M.R. spectrum showed $\delta_{TMS}^{CO^1_4} = 0.8\text{--}1.0$ ppm (3 methyl group), 4.71, 4.52 ppm (terminal methylene) Lit. reports $\delta_{TMS}^{CO^1_4} = 0.8\text{--}1.0$ and 4.71, 4.52 ppm¹. (Found : C, 87.85; H, 12.15; Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}$: C, 88.2; H, 11.82%).

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